

THE DETERMINATION OF THE PARACHORS OF INORGANIC SALTS IN SOLUTIONS AND THEIR STRUCTURE.

PART I. POTASSIUM SALTS.

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Hanmick and Andrew's equation for calculating the parachor of mixtures of two liquids has been modified to apply to the calculation of parachor of solid inorganic salts in solution.

The parachor values of 15 salts found in many cases are in good agreement with the calculated $\Sigma[P]$ of the salts concerned.

The atomic parachor of potassium is found to be (110) in the case of monovalent salts and (106) when the salt is bivalent containing two atoms of potassium.

The parachor values of the 9 potassium salts : carbonate, bicarbonate, pyrosulphate, chromate, chlorate, bromate, perchlorate, cyanide and sulphocyanide which have not been previously determined are now found by this method.

Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) have shown that the parachors of substances unstable in the pure liquid state can be calculated from the surface tensions and densities of their solutions in solvents of known parachor on the assumption that the parachors of solvent and solutes are additive. Thus parachors of the solutes have been calculated by finding the parachors P_m of a solution containing a molecular fraction x of the solute, in a solvent of known parachor, by means of the equation.

$$P_m = (1-x) P_p + x P_x$$

where P is the unknown parachor of the solute to be determined, P_p is the parachor of the solvent (already known), and x is the molecular fraction of the solute.

The "straight line mixture law" of Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*) has been found in several cases to be independent of dilution. In other cases, where the value of the solute parachor P_x changes with the dilution, the parachor of the pure solute has been deduced from a series of values of P_x by straight line extrapolation.

Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 671) pointed out the applicability of the 'straight line mixture law' in the determination of parachor of organic solids dissolved in liquids. But in all this and subsequent work no attempt has been made to determine the parachor of solid inorganic substances in solution and of such other salts which are difficult to fuse or which decompose before fusion.

The authors have kept the above object in view in their investigations and have shown from the experimental work that by modification of the Hammick and Andrew's equation, the parachor of very many inorganic salts and elements, which have not been previously determined, could be accurately calculated from the measurement of density and surface tension of their solutions.

In the true solutions or completely miscible mixtures, the solute (liquid or solid) is believed to be dispersed in the solvent in the molecular or ionic condition, and therefore in solution the usual distinction between the liquid state and the solid state entirely disappears. There is one difference, however, that when two liquids are mixed (or one dissolved into the other) the total volume of the mixture is generally equal to the sum of the individual volumes of the two components. But when a solid is dissolved in a solvent the volume of the solution in many cases (neglecting a small change in volume) is practically identical with the volume originally taken. Therefore, since according to Sugden's equation,

$$P = V \cdot \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where V is the molecular volume, or as in Hammick and Andrew's equation (*loc. cit.*)

$$P_m = V_m \cdot \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where V_m is the mean molecular volume, the parachor values calculated by the above equation, when inorganic salts are dissolved in the solvent (water), will be half as when liquids are dissolved. Consequently Hammick and Andrew's equation, when applied to the inorganic salt solutes in solution and when volume changes are negligible, should be written as

$$P_m = (1-x) P_p + x \frac{P_s}{2}.$$

The measured values of the parachor, obtained with a variety of salts dissolved in water, indicate that the mixture law, as modified in accordance with the above view, correctly holds and the values obtained are also identical with those calculated from the atomic and structural parachors of the compounds concerned.

The parachor is found to be independent of the concentration up to the lower limit of 0.009 g. mol. of the solute per 100 g. of the solvent. The more dilute solutions containing less than 0.009 g. per 100 g. of the solvent were not found to yield the correct parachor values.

With such solutions of solids, where the volume changes take place to a considerable extent, the value of P_s changes with the concentration and the parachor of the solute is then deduced from a series of the values

of P_x by straight line extrapolation as pointed out by Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

In this investigation the surface tension has been measured by the double capillary rise method in the manner described by Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1483).

All determinations were made at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm .2$ maintained in a self regulated thermostat. Extra pure salts of Merck or Kahlbaum have been used throughout.

The solutions were made by dissolving a weighed quantity of an anhydrous salt in 100 g. of distilled water thus ensuring the same content of water in all solutions. If the solution is made up to a definite volume, the water content of the solution will vary according as the solution contracts or expands (Mogan and McKirahan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1760). Great care was taken to expose the solution as little as possible to the atmosphere to avoid any fine stray dust particles from getting into the solution.

In those cases, where the anhydrous salt was not available or the water of crystallisation could not be completely removed or the solubility of the salt was considerably altered on becoming anhydrous, the hydrated salt was used for making the solution, but the weight of the water of crystallisation was subtracted from the total weight of the salt, and the same added to the quantity of water used as solvent.

The densities of solutions were measured at $30^\circ \pm .2$ by using a specific gravity bottle of 10 c.c. capacity.

For calculating the sum of the atomic parachors, use has been made of the atomic and structural parachors, given in Sugden's book ("The Parachor and Valency," pp., 38, 131, 181).

The results of 15 potassium salts are recorded in columns 1 to 10 of the following table.

A reference to columns 7 and 8 indicates that the figures of the measured parachor agree very closely with those of the calculated parachor, except in the case of potassium carbonate. The deficit in this case is probably due to the formation of a stable hydrate of carbonate in contact with water. (*cf. Mellor, "Modern Inorganic Chemistry," p. 810.*)

In column 9 are given for comparison the values of parachor obtained by the fusion method by Sugden and Wilkins. Only the parachors of KBr and $K_2Cr_2O_7$ agree with the calculated values. In other cases the experi-

TABLE I.
Results obtained with solutions of different potassium salts.

Substance.	X (Molar frac- tion of so- lute)	D (Density of solution).	γ (Surface tension of the soln.).	M_m (Mean mol. wt.)	P_m (Measured parachor of the soln.)	P_x (observed parachor of the so- lute com- pound).	$X[P]$ (Calc. parachor of the so- lute com- pound).	Parachor of the compound observed by Sargent and Wilkins by fu- sion method. ⁴	Parachor of K used in cal- culating $X[P]$.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.
KCl	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0682 \\ 0.0691 \end{array} \right.$	1.135 1.130	76.75 77.91	21.312 21.565	55.56 55.69	161.2 161.9	162.7	136.6	110
KBr	0.0434	1.188	75.39	22.386	55.49	174.48	176.4	174.3	110
KI	0.0368	1.225	71.61	23.451	55.67	200.0	199.4	205.2	110
KNO ₃	0.0466	1.130	74.47	21.538	55.98	201.3	200.9	189	110
K ₂ CO ₃ (anhydrous)	0.03765	1.201	87.67	21.516	57.35	286.4	293.6	Not done	106
KHCO ₃	0.03474	1.106	76.86	20.854	55.84	214.2	208.7	Not done	110
K ₂ SO ₄	0.01227	1.074	79.29	19.914	55.35	329.2	330.6	328.0	106
K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ (at 35°)	0.02702	1.208	84.03	22.761	57.07	335.4	336.8	Not done	106

(mean 161.8)

TABLE I (contd.)^s

Substance.	X (molar frac- tion of so- lute).	D (Density of solution).	γ (Surface tension of the soln.)	M _m (Mean mol. wt.).	P _m (Measured parachor of the solu- tion).	P _z (observed parachor of the solu- tion comp.).	$\bar{\alpha}$ [P] (Calcula- ted para- chor of the solute comp.).	8.	9.	Parachor of the compound observed by Sugden and Wilkins by fu- sion method. [†]	Parachor of K used in calculating $\bar{\alpha}$ [P].
KClO ₃ *	0.02157	1.089	68.05	20.252	53.4	218.0	217.9	Not done	110		110
KBrO ₃ *	0.01522	1.104	68.83	20.368	53.79	231.2					
	0.02111	1.138	68.93	21.145	53.53	233.0	231.6	Not done	110		110
						(mean 232.1)					
KClO ₄ *	0.01029	1.043	67.75	19.235	52.86	237.2	236.3	Not done	110		110
KCN	0.06465	1.097	73.14	21.048	56.08	172.36	172.3	Not done	110		110
KCN ₅	0.03574	1.085	72.36	20.832	55.98	218.8	218.9	Not done	110		110
K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	0.009101	1.096	77.76	20.505	55.55	450.6	451.2	450.8**	106		106
K ₂ S ₂ O ₇	0.02086	1.201	82.36	22.928	57.45	439.4	438.8	Not done	106		106

* As these salts are not sufficiently soluble at the ordinary temperature to contain the required molar fraction of the solute, they were determined at the temperature of 66°.

** *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 263).

† *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1292).

mentally determined values of the parachor by fusion method are either too high or too low. It is also seen that the solution method measures the parachor very accurately of the salts like KClO_3 , KBrO_3 , KClO_4 , KCN , KCNS , K_2CrO_4 , and $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$, which decompose before fusion.

In calculating $\Sigma[P]$ of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$, the structures given below have been found to fit in with the measured parachor values.

Potassium dichromate.

Potassium pyrosulphate.

In column 10, it will be observed that in calculating the $\Sigma[P]$ of monovalent salts, the figure (110) as the atomic parachor of potassium has been used. This value has been deduced by Sugden from the study of several salts in their fused state (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1291). On the other hand in calculating $\Sigma[P]$ of the bivalent salts, the value of (106) for the atomic parachor has been employed. This value again is that deduced from Jaeger's data of surface tensions and densities of halides and sulphates of potassium (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 1). In computing the $\Sigma[P]$ of potassium dichromate, Friemann and Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 263) have made use of the constant (106) for potassium. In this connection it will be of interest to mention that the observed parachor of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, leads to the parachor value of (110) for potassium and that of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, gives the value of (106) as the atomic parachor for the metal. It thus appears that when odd number of potassium atoms are present in a salt the parachor constant equals to (110), whilst when the salt contains an even number of potassium atoms, the parachor corresponds to (106). It is difficult to assign any explanation for this peculiarity at present, nor is there any conclusive evidence in the case of other monovalent atoms showing similar behaviour.

The "solution method" is being extended to the determination of parachor of several soluble inorganic salts of sodium, lithium, rubidium, magnesium, strontium, barium, manganese, iron, cobalt, nickel, etc., the results of which will be published in subsequent papers. The atomic parachor of the metal is also deduced therefrom.